

Supporting information

Relaxing the Goldschmidt tolerance factor:
sizable incorporation of the guanidinium
cation into a two-dimensional Ruddlesden-
Popper perovskite

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Experimental Section

Starting materials

All starting materials for synthesis were commercially purchased. Phenethylammonium iodide 98% (PEAI), Methylammonium iodide 98% (MAI) and Guanidinium iodide 99% (Gual) were purchased from Great Cell Solar and Lead iodide 99% (PbI_2) was purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI). *N,N*-Dimethylformamide (DMF) 99.8% Extra Dry over Molecular Sieve, AcroSeal, Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) 99.7% Extra Dry over Molecular Sieve, AcroSeal and Chlorobenzene Extra Dry over Molecular Sieve, AcroSeal were purchased from ACROS ORGANICS. TiO_2 paste (DSL 30NR-D, batch 438) and Ethanol Absolute Dry (max. 0.02% water) were supplied by DYESOL and PanReac AppliChem, respectively. Titanium diisopropoxide bis (acetylacetonate) solution (75% in 2-propanol), Lithium bis (trifluoromethylsulphonyl)imide (LiTFSI), 4-tert-butylpyridine (TBP), Cobal (III) FK209 TFSI, Spiro-MeOTAD, Acetonitrile (ACN) 99.9% and Dimethyl sulfoxide- d_6 (d-DMSO) 99.9 were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. This starting batch did not need additional purification and were used for all syntheses. All the organics salts and the PbI_2 was stored in an inert atmosphere (N_2).

The glass patterned with fluorine tin oxide (FTO) TEC-15 and amorphous glass were purchased from Pilkington. For the cleaning process, Isopropyl alcohol (technical grade, 99.5%) and the soap (decon90) were purchased from PanReac AppliChem and Decon, respectively.

Film fabrication

Substrate preparation

All substrates (FTO and amorphous glass, 2 x 2 cm) were cleaning with a toothbrush and decon90 to remove all the dirty from the surfaces, then were sonicated sequentially in 3 steps:

1. - MilliQ water with decon90 (~2% V/V) for 15 min
2. - MilliQ water for 15 min
3. - Isopropyl alcohol for 15 min

The substrates were treated with ultraviolet ozone for 15 min before the deposition.

TiO_2 deposition

In order to facilitate the subsequent deposition of the perovskite a 150 nm thick mesoporous TiO_2 layer was prepared by spin coating on the FTO from a dilute dispersion of TiO_2 in ethanol, 1:8 by weight ratio, at 2000 rpm, 1000 rpm/s for 15 s followed by a

sintering stage as shown in the Table 1. Different heating ramps were used so as not to cause thermal shock to the C-TiO₂ and m-TiO₂ layers, which would cause cracks and short circuit of the device. The same recipe as in previous works was used to achieve the final temperature at 500 °C during 20 min.^{1,2}

Table S1. Heating ramps for TiO₂

Ramp (min)	5	5	5	5	5
Final Temperature (°C)	125	250	350	450	500
Heating time (min)	10	5	5	10	20

Perovskite synthesis

The precursor solutions were prepared considering the amounts showed in Table 2. The precursors were dissolved in different steps:

1. The PbI₂ was dissolved using 0.5 ml of DMF or different ratios of DMF:DMSO and heated in a hot plate at 70 °C with continuous stirring for at least ~1 h.
2. Solution was transferred to a second vial with MAI. The solution was stirring without heating for ~30 min.
3. Solution was transferred to a third vial with PEA I. The solution was stirring without heating for ~30 min.
4. Solution was transferred to the last vial with Gua I (it is important to dissolve the Gua in the last step to prevent losses, see text below). The solution was stirring without heating for ~30 min.

All solutions were filtered by a 0.22 µm pore size, hydrophobic PTFE membrane.

We have carried out ¹H NMR experiments to all our initial precursor solutions after transfer and filtration to assess the MA⁺:Gua⁺ ratio. Figure S1 displays the ¹H-NMR spectra with the main peaks attributed to the MA, PEA and Gua cations. It is clearly observed the linear rise of the signal at 6.88 ppm (assigned to the NH₂- groups of the Gua cation) when increasing the Gua content which is in line with the decrease of the signal at 2.37 ppm associated to the CH₃- group in the MA cations. The relative ratio of both signals can be used to determine the percentage of each cation in the solution (integration of the peaks). Table S3 indicates the relative ratio obtained from the NMR measurements and the theoretical values fixed in the weighting. The good agreement in between both numbers for all samples proves that no significance losses are produced during the preparation of the precursor solutions.

Table S2. Amount in mmol of each reagent for each initial stoichiometry in the precursor solution ($n = 2, 3$ and 4).

n = 2					
%Gua	mmol Pbl ₂	mmol MAI	mmol PEAI	mmol Gual	V (mL)
0	0.300	0.150	0.300	0.000	0.5
5	0.300	0.143	0.300	0.007	0.5
10	0.300	0.135	0.300	0.015	0.5
15	0.300	0.128	0.300	0.022	0.5
20	0.300	0.120	0.300	0.030	0.5

n = 3					
%Gua	mmol Pbl ₂	mmol MAI	mmol PEAI	mmol Gual	V (mL)
0	0.300	0.200	0.200	0.000	0.5
5	0.300	0.190	0.200	0.010	0.5
10	0.300	0.180	0.200	0.020	0.5
15	0.300	0.170	0.200	0.030	0.5
20	0.300	0.160	0.200	0.040	0.5
25	0.300	0.150	0.200	0.050	0.5
30	0.300	0.140	0.200	0.060	0.5
40	0.300	0.120	0.200	0.080	0.5
50	0.300	0.100	0.200	0.100	0.5
60	0.300	0.080	0.200	0.120	0.5
70	0.300	0.060	0.200	0.140	0.5
80	0.300	0.040	0.200	0.160	0.5
90	0.300	0.020	0.200	0.180	0.5

n = 4					
%Gua	mmol Pbl ₂	mmol MAI	mmol PEAI	mmol Gual	V (mL)
0	0.300	0.225	0.150	0.000	0.5
10	0.300	0.203	0.150	0.023	0.5
20	0.300	0.180	0.150	0.045	0.5
40	0.300	0.135	0.150	0.009	0.5

Perovskite deposition

The perovskite films have been deposited by the hot casting (HC) temperature method. The substrates used in each case were heated at different temperatures (25, 50, 75, 90, 100 and 120 °C) on a hot plate for 10 min. Then, they were moved quickly on the spin coater and 50 µl of the precursor solution was deposited in static on the substrates. The spin coating condition are 5000 rpm for 30 seconds. The resulting films were annealed at 100 °C on a hot plate for 20 minutes.

Device fabrication

Perovskite solar cells were fabricated on FTO substrates previously cleaned by a sequential sonication treatment. A compact blocking layer of TiO₂ (30 nm in thickness) was then deposited onto FTO glass substrate by spray pyrolysis, using a titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) solution in ethanol (60% v/v), and then sintered at 450 °C for 30 min. A 150-nm-thick layer of mesoporous TiO₂ was prepared by spin-coating a diluted TiO₂ dispersion in ethanol, ratio 1:8 by weight, at 2000 rpm for 15 s followed by a sintering step at 500 °C for 30 min. The perovskite films have been deposited by the hot casting (HC) temperature method as indicated above. After this, spiro-OMeTAD was spin-coated at 4000 rpm, for 30 s from a chlorobenzene solution (28.9 mg in 400 µL) containing Li-TFSI (7.0 µL from a 520 mg ml⁻¹ stock solution in acetonitrile), TBP (11.5 µl) and Co(III)TFSI (8.8 µL from a 40 mg ml⁻¹ stock solution) as dopants. Finally, a 70 nm gold electrode was evaporated.

Synthesis of Powders

All the perovskite powders were synthesized by grinding an organic salt (MAI, PEAI and GuaI) and PbI₂ (total amount of 0.5 g) in an electric ball mill for 30 min at 900 rpm (Retsch, model: EMAX, stainless steel grinding jar with a volume of 125 ml and 10 stainless steel balls, diameter size 20 mm), considering for all the % Gua the formula PEA₂(MA_{1-x}Gua_x)₂Pb₃I₁₀. The synthesis was performed under ambient conditions, 25 °C, 40-50% RH. The resulting powders were stored in a nitrogen environment inside the glove box.

Characterization

X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements

X-ray diffraction experiments for all the samples were performed using a Bruker D8 DISCOVER diffractometer operating at 40 kV and 40 mA and using Cu Kα radiation (1.54060 Å). The range of measurement was done from 2° to 40° Bragg angles.

GIWAXS measurements

GIWAXS measurements were performed in a Bruker Discover diffractometer equipped with a Cu microsource with a 1 mm pinhole collimator, an eulerian cradle and an area detector Pilatus 100K. A 2theta range between 10-50 degrees was used.

UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy

The measurement of the films (glass/FTO/TiO₂/RP perovskite) was performed at room temperature (~25 °C) using a UV-VIS spectrometer CARY 100. The range of the measurement was from 500 to 800 nm in all cases.

Steady-state and time-resolved PL measurements

Steady-state photoluminescence spectra were recorded with a FLS980 (Edinburgh Instruments) fluorescence spectrometer using a 450 W Xe1 xenon arc lamp and a R298P photomultiplier as detector. Time resolved fluorescence measurements were accomplished through the time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) technique, by using the same FLS980 (Edinburgh Instruments) photoluminescence spectrometer. The samples were excited at 406.4 nm with a 86.8 ps pulse width diode laser using a R2658P photomultiplier as the detector.

Scanning Electron Microscopy studies

The morphology of the thin films was studied by using Scanning Electron Microscopy (JEOL JSM 7800F) using a LED detector with 2 kV electric potential. The work distances were ~6.6 mm for all cases and x2000 magnification.

FTIR spectroscopy

The FTIR spectroscopy analysis was realized using a spectrometer FTIR-ATR Perkin-Elmer Spectrum Two. The spectrum was analyzed in the range of 450–4000 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and a total of 40 scans were collected.

Computational details

Periodic DFT-GGA calculations using the PBE exchange correlation functional were performed. Electron-ion interactions were described by ultrasoft pseudopotentials. In case of the Pb atom we used a scalar relativistic pseudopotential. The k-point meshes with grid spacing of $2\pi \times 0.02 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ or less are used for Brillouin zone integration. The Mal, Gual and PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ structures were used from the bibliography without further optimization.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) measurements

NMR spectra were performed in Bruker Advance spectrometers (300 MHz in ^1H), using a deuterated solvent. The values of the chemical shifts (δ) are quantified as parts per million (ppm).

Figure S1. ^1H NMR spectra of the initial precursor solutions after transfer and filtration to assess the MA⁺:Gua⁺ ratio.

Table S3. Theoretical and experimental percentages of Gua obtained from the ^1H NMR spectra for each initial precursor solution prepared for the fabrication of the mixed cation PEA₂(MA_{1-x}Gua_x)₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskite films.

% Gua from weighting	0%	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	100%
% Gua from ^1H -NMR	0	16%	23%	34%	41%	52%	59%	70%	79%	90%	100%

Figure S2. Absorption spectra (A) and X-ray diffraction patterns (B) of films of PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ prepared at different hot-casting temperatures, 25 °C, 55 °C, 70 °C, 90 °C, 100 °C and 120 °C.

Figure S3. Top-surface SEM images of the PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskite film prepared at different hot-casting temperatures, 25 °C (A), 55 °C (B), 70 °C (C), 90 °C (D), 100 °C (E) and 120 °C (F). Scale bar, 10 μm in the overall image and 1 μm in the enlarged image (top right corner).

Figure S4. X-ray diffraction patterns in logarithmic scale (A) and linear scale showing only the more intense peaks (B) of films of $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ prepared from different solvents: DMF (black line) and DMF:DMSO ratio of 9:1 (blue line), 7:3 (red line) and 5:5 (orange line). The XRD pattern of a MAPbI_3 film is displayed in panel B (green line).

Figure S5. Absorption spectra (A) and X-ray diffraction patterns (B) of films of $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ prepared with different concentrations of the initial precursor solution: 1.2 M (red line), 0.8 M (orange line), 0.6 M (black line) and 0.4 M (blue line).

Figure S6. XRD patterns of the PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskite films (in logarithmic scale) upon addition of different Gua content: from 5% to 90%.

Figure S7. Absorption spectra (A and C) and X-ray diffraction patterns (B and D) of the PEA₂MAPb₂I₇ (A and B) and the PEA₂MA₃Pb₄I₁₃ (C and D) perovskite films upon addition of different Gua content: 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 30% and 40%.

Figure S8. X-ray diffraction patterns of powders of mixed cation PEA₂(MA_{1-x}Gua_x)₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskite with Gua contents of 0%, 5%, 15%, 20%, and 25%. The simulated XRD pattern of the PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskite is also shown for comparison.

Figure S9. Experimental infrared spectra of several perovskite films: $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (black line), $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.90}\text{Gua}_{0.10})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (purple line), $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.80}\text{Gua}_{0.20})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (blue line), $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.60}\text{Gua}_{0.40})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (yellow line), Gua_2PbI_4 (green line) and $\text{MA}_{0.90}\text{Gua}_{0.10}\text{PbI}_3$ (brown line).

Figure S10. 2D GIWAXS patterns of mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with 30% (A), 40% (B), 50% (C), 60% (D), 70% (E), 80% (F), 90% (G) and 100% (H) Gua content.

Figure S11. Optimized simulated structure of the 2D RP $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (left), $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.75}\text{Gua}_{0.25})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (middle) and $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.50}\text{Gua}_{0.50})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (right). The Gua cations are represented in a ball (atoms) and stick (bonds) configuration while the PEA and MA cations are represented with lines.

Figure S12. Top-surface SEM images of $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with different Gua contents: 5% (A), 10% (B), 15% (C), 25% (D), 30% (E), 50% (F), 60% (G), 70% (H) 80% (I) and 100% (J). Scale bar, 2 μm .

Figure S13. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP PEA₂MA₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskite film.

Figure S14. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP PEA₂(MA_{0.70}Gua_{0.30})₂Pb₃I₁₀ perovskite film.

Figure S15. EDX profile analysis (upper panel) and elemental mapping (lower panel) of the 2D RP $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.20}\text{Gua}_{0.80})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite film.

Table S4. Atomic percentages of C, Pb and I obtained from the EDX analysis of the different mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite films

% Gua	C (Atomic %)	Pb (Atomic %)	I (Atomic %)
0	61.99	4.98	16.18
5	58.66	5.55	17.65
10	58.11	5.62	17.82
15	58.81	5.06	16.21
20	62.40	5.72	18.42
25	61.86	5.60	18.03
30	60.26	5.38	17.18
40	60.72	4.67	14.38
50	63.40	4.71	14.79
60	64.71	5.39	17.13
70	62.85	5.03	15.79
80	62.98	5.02	15.96
90	63.85	5.80	17.41
100	60.91	4.45	16.25

Figure S16. Time-resolved PL signal at the maximum of each peak of $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with different Gua contents: from 0% to 80%.

Table S5. PL time constants (τ) and relative amplitudes (a) derived from a triexponential fit of the experimental of $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with different Gua contents. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 405$ nm. $E_{\text{exc}} = 1 \mu\text{J}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$

% Gua	τ_1 / ns	a_1 / %	τ_2 / ns	a_2 / %	τ_3 / ns	a_3 / %	τ_{av} / ns
0	1.28	28	9.0	43	73	29	25.4
5	0.66	27	13.9	26	154	47	76.2
10	1.02	25	14.1	30	214	45	100.8
15	1.87	22	11.9	33	92	45	45.7
20	2.51	15	17.5	31	160	54	92.2
25	2.46	15	17.2	32	149	53	84.4
30	3.32	14	19.7	35	133	51	75.2
40	4.48	13	24.2	37	141	50	80.0
50	3.18	11	33.8	33	369	56	218.1
60	1.15	32	9.07	35	100	33	36.5
80	0.36	43	4.31	33	39	24	10.9

Figure S17. Transient absorption spectra at different delay times (A and B) and decays at $\lambda_{\text{probe}} = 570 \text{ nm}$, 612 nm , 650 nm and 710 nm (D and F) of mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with 10% (A and C) and 50% (B and B) Gua content. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400 \text{ nm}$

Figure S18. Photographs of mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 40% and 60% Gua content taken at different days after their preparation.

Figure S19. XRD patterns of five mixed cation $\text{PEA}_2(\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{Gua}_x)_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ perovskite films with 0% (black line), 10% (purple line), 20% (blue line), 40% (yellow line) and 60% (orange line) Gua content measured at different days after their preparation.

Bibliography

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